

Approach on the study and mitigation of scattered light in Advanced Virgo Plus

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Abstract

Scattered light that re-couples with the main beam of current gravitational wave detectors is a major limitation of their sensitivity, especially at low frequencies. The detector noise depends on the amount of scattered light that is actually produced and the relative movement of the optical benches producing scattered light and the main interferometer beam. This work reports the approach followed in Virgo to study and mitigate this noise source.

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Introduction

Scattered light is one of the major limitations to the sensitivity of gravitational wave interferometric detectors such as LIGO [1] and Virgo [2]. It has been observed that scattered light can re-couple with the interferometer's main beam, degrading its performance [3, 4, 5]. However, the study and simulation of scattered light sources are difficult. In preparation of the next observing run O4, the approach described in this work has been followed to study and mitigate scattered light sources in Virgo. The scattered light produces noise on the detector's sensitivity due to the phase modulation introduced by the relative motion between the scattering object and the detector and also due to the radiation pressure modulation. The amplitude of this noise also depends on the fraction of scattered light that actually re-couples with the main beam of the detector. The effect in terms of noise on the sensitivity curve of the detector [6] is given by

$$h_{noise}(t) = \sqrt{f_r} \cdot \left\{ K_\phi(f) \cdot \mathcal{F} \left[\sin \left(\frac{4\pi}{\lambda} x(t) \right) \right] + K_{\delta P/P}(f) \cdot \mathcal{F} \left[\cos \left(\frac{4\pi}{\lambda} x(t) \right) \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

where f_r is the fraction of re-coupled scattered light, \mathcal{F} represents the Fourier Transform, $K_\phi(f)$ and $K_{\delta P/P}(f)$ are the phase and amplitude quadratures of the interferometer optical transfer functions, λ is the laser wavelength, $x(t)$ is the motion of the scatterer relative to the interferometer beam.

The factor f_r receives several contributions

$$f_r = f_{sc} + f_{sp} + f_{Rayleigh} + f_{extra} \quad (2)$$

where f_{sc} accounts for the scattered light, f_{sp} for the specular reflection, $f_{Rayleigh}$ represents the light scattered by atoms or molecules (in crystals for example), f_{extra} is the extra contribution of scattered light coming from spurious beams.

The factor f_{sc} is an intrinsic contribution of each optical element and is related to the bi-directional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) of the surface by means of the simplified relationship [6], demonstrated in [7],

$$f_{sc} \sim \frac{\text{BRDF} \cdot \lambda^2}{\pi \omega^2} \quad (3)$$

where ω is the beam radius at the scattering surface. This contribution cannot be eliminated, but it can be reduced by improving the surface quality of optics used. Since it is not easy to make numerical simulations of this quantity, the strategy used is to directly measure this parameter experimentally as will be described below.

The factor f_{sp} is the light back reflected towards the interferometer by specular reflection [6] and it is given by

$$f_{sp} = \frac{\alpha R^2 z_R^2 \exp \left[-\frac{2\pi D^2 z_R \beta^2}{2\lambda} \left(\frac{1}{D^2 + z_R^2} + \frac{1}{(D-R)^2 + z_R^2} \right) \right]}{(D^2 + z_R^2) [(D-R)^2 + z_R^2]} \quad (4)$$

where α is the reflectivity of the optics, R is the radius of curvature of the reflecting surface, D is the distance between the surface and the beam waist, z_R is the beam Rayleigh range and β is the small angle at which the optic is tilted. The elements that reflect the most are the lenses. Since this amount decreases exponentially as a function of the angle at which the elements are tilted β , the lenses have almost all been tilted by at least a hundred μ rads to make this contribution negligible.

The factor $f_{Rayleigh}$ arises from the scattering of light by structures in the bulk material of the optic much smaller than the wavelength of the radiation, like crystals. In Virgo's optical systems, this type of scattering occurs from the TGG crystals within the Faraday Isolators and the output mode cleaner cavity (Suprasil 3001) [8].

The factor f_{extra} refers to the scattered light that re-couples with the main beam coming from a different source than the contributions just described. Actually, in Virgo's optical systems, spurious beams propagate and are reflected by vacuum chambers, optical mounts, optics or other elements, generating scattered light with large phase modulation. The ghost beams propagate through the system and can re-couple with the interferometer beam. By tracing these beams, called ghost beams, it is possible to mitigate them before they can produce scattered light that is dangerous for the detector.

In this work, the effect of the scattered light from the suspended benches during the observing run O3 is shown as well as the simulated effect of this noise for the observing run O4. It is recalled how it is possible to quantify f_{sc} coming from optical elements experimentally and how the study and mitigation of ghost beams in Virgo has been performed.

Scattered light from suspended benches

The factors responsible for the noise due to scattered light are, as shown in Eq. 1, $x(t)$ and f_r . In Virgo, the interferometer mirrors are suspended with superattenuators [9] and also the benches containing the optics and photodiodes are suspended [10]. The latter are a source of scattered light as they contain scattering elements, whose produced scattered light re-couples with the interferometer beam due to the relative motion $x(t)$. The relative motion between the suspended benches (carrying the scattering element) and the detector (the interferometer suspended optics close to the considered bench)

can easily be calculated from reconstructed signals. The factor f_r can be calculated from scattered light measurements by enhancing in a controlled way the motion of the bench while measuring the bench motion and the amount of noise produced in the interferometer, as was done for O3 [11]. The comparison between the projection measured from a noise injection on suspended benches in O3 and the simulated projections for O4 is shown in Fig. 1. From a fit of Eq. 1 to the data of the noise injection done during O3, one can calculate the recoupling factor f_r for the different benches. On the left side of Fig. 1, the example of the detection bench SDB1 is shown. The factor f_r for this bench has been calculated to be 0.002 ppm. In the simulation, the transfer functions describe the interferometer as it will be during O4 and the relative motion $x(t)$ is calculated from the reconstructed signals during the commissioning for O4 [12], associated to large sea microseism. On the right side of Fig. 1, the simulated projection for the bench SDB1, using the same recoupling factor measured during O3, is shown. It can be seen that in case of high seismic motion, the effect of scattered light for O4 is spoiling the goal sensitivity below 12 Hz. This is the motivation to reduce the amount the re-coupled fraction of scattered light f_r .

Another way to calculate the fraction of scattered light that couples with the interferometer is to sum the contributions of the different coupling mechanisms shown in Eq. 2. The most limiting factor is f_{sc} , which is difficult to be known for most of the optical elements. Moreover, it is not easy to simulate with the available computational tools. The currently easiest way to derive this factor is to measure it experimentally. Before O4, it is planned to simulate the scattered light noise projections with the exact f_r values for each suspended bench and see if it is possible to take action to decrease the coupling factor.

Figure 1: On the left, the scattered light projection coming from the detection suspended bench SDB1 fitted to the measured coupling during noise injection performed in O3 [11]. On the right, the scattered light projection considering the interferometer transfer function computed with O4 parameters and the same f_r factor with respect to the O3 projection [12].

Measurement of scattered light

The fraction of light scattered by an optical element that re-couples with the incident beam can be measured using an interferometric back-scattermeter such as the one built at LAPP, shown in Fig. 2 and described in [7].

Figure 2: Back-scatter meter experiment set up at LAPP [7].

A laser beam at $\lambda = 1064$ nm propagates towards a 50/50 beam splitter where the transmitted part will be used as a local oscillator (LO) for homodyne detection. The reflected beam, on the other hand, propagates up to the scattering sample of which one wants to measure the f_{sc} i.e. the BRDF. The sample is free to move along the direction of the beam, as it is mounted on a small bench suspended from four metal wires. The sample is tilted to a similar angle as the corresponding optic or element on Virgo optical benches. The scattered light is reflected back to the homodyne where it couples with the LO and by differential measurement f_{sc} can be calculated as the variance of the quantity [7]:

$$A(t) = \frac{P_1(t) - P_2(t)}{P_1(t) + P_2(t)} = \sqrt{2f_{sc}} \cos\left(2\pi \frac{\Delta L(t)}{\lambda}\right) \quad (5)$$

where $P_{1,2}(t)$ are the powers detected by the homodyne photodiodes and $\Delta L(t)$ is the position modulation of the scattering sample. With this setup it has been possible to measure back-scattered light for incidence angles larger than $500 \mu\text{rad}$ with an angular resolution of $160 \mu\text{rad}$ [7]. First BRDFs of highly scattering elements were characterised, to verify the functioning of the setup. Therefore, it was possible to measure the BRDFs of the elements that could be more critical on the benches such as the photodiodes (either the photodiode sensor or the protection window in front of it) and quadrants.

Mitigation of spurious beams

It has been observed that there are spurious beams which re-couple with the interferometer that increase scattered light noise. These beams are called *ghost beams* and originate from the fact that the coatings of the optical elements are not perfect but have residual reflections or transmissions. Using a software called *Optocad* [13], which is a Fortran 95 module for tracing Gaussian TEM00 beams through an optical set-up, it is possible to trace the ghost beams and see where they propagate through Virgo's

benches. An example of a beam propagating in an optical set-up on Optocad is shown in Fig. 3. The beam is almost completely reflected by a mirror. However, a fraction of the beam is transmitted from the outer surface as the high reflective coating has residual transmission (of the order of a few to hundreds of ppm). Subsequently, this beam arrives at the back surface and is partially reflected (a fraction ranging from hundreds of ppm to 1%, depending on how the surface is coated). The ghost beam generated in this way leaves the first surface and propagates on the optical bench, free to hit reflective elements and produce scattered light. At that point this light can re-couple with the interferometer beam and this effect can be seen on the projection in Eq. 1.

Figure 3: A beam propagating towards a mirror. A ghost beam is generated at the mirror surface. A diaphragm let the reflected beam propagate and it dumps the ghost beam.

The approach taken for this study was to trace the ghost beams from each optical element of the suspended benches with Optocad and calculate their power from the residual transmittivity η_T and reflectivity η_R [14, 15, 16]. For example the power of the ghost beam in Fig. 3 can be computed from

$$P_{GB} = \eta_R \cdot \eta_T^2 \cdot P_{in} \quad (6)$$

where P_{in} is the input beam power. It has been decided to dump the beams that were about to hit critical elements or the more powerful ones by using absorbing surfaces along their path. Several mitigation strategies have been adopted, depending on several constraints: optimisation of the wedge of the optics, installation of diaphragms (whose aperture was optimised so as not to introduce losses to the main beam), installation of baffles in the system tubes, installation of small beam dumps, use of absorbing screws, dumpers mechanically attached or glued to photodiodes and quadrants, installation of absorbing disks behind the mirrors to stop spurious transmitted beams. All these strategies were implemented during the commissioning between O3 and O4. The overall effect of these actions will be assessed during O4 by remeasuring the f_r factor.

Conclusions

Scattered light has been shown to be one of the major limitations of the sensitivity of gravitational wave detectors. To reduce its impact on Virgo detector, it has been decided to approach this topic from different points of view. First the scattered light noise coming from suspended benches projections measured during O3 have been used to identify scattering elements. From them it has been optimized the optical setup and the simulations of the O4 scattered noise projections are being carried on. This quantifies the actual coupling of the interferometer to scattered light. The work carried out at the level

of the suspensions allows to reduce the residual movement between the suspended components so as to reduce the range of frequencies affected by this noise.

To better estimate the coupling coefficient of the scattered light with the beam of the interferometer, an interferometric back-scattermeter has been built to be able to measure it directly and to estimate more precisely the scattered light coming from each optical element. Finally, a full campaign of simulations and mitigation of ghost beams has been carried out on Virgo's benches, to significantly reduce their contribution to the overall effect of scattered light on the detector. During the run O4, it will be possible to appreciate the impact of the efforts explained in this work. However, new strategies to mitigate scattered light in gravitational wave detectors will continue to be sought in order to increase current interferometers sensitivity and their observation range for astronomical GW sources.

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